

Artificial Neural Networks for Predicting Asphalt Fatigue Life: Investigating Material and Loading Parameters with a Comprehensive Dataset and Addressing Model Intricacies

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Abstract This study employs artificial neural networks (ANNs) to predict the fatigue life of asphalt concrete (AC), crucial for road maintenance and longevity. Leveraging a dataset from extensive laboratory tests, we optimized ANN models to address the variability in AC fatigue data. Our approach involved fine-tuning hyperparameters and adapting network architectures to best utilize a dataset of 152 samples. The models were trained with both linear and logarithmic loss functions. Results showed that modified bituminous binders significantly improve fatigue life predictions, with comprehensive input parameters being vital for accurate modeling. Although models achieved moderate overall R^2 scores of about 0.4, they highlighted the significant impact of binder type and content on prediction outcomes. The research demonstrates the potential of machine learning to enhance pavement engineering by providing deeper insights into AC fatigue life. Optimized models and codes are available in an open repository, encouraging further exploration and application.

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1 Introduction

Asphalt concrete (AC) serves as a fundamental material in road pavement construction, composed of aggregates like crushed aggregate, gravel, or sand, combined with a bituminous binder derived from the distillation of crude oil or enhanced with polymers and additives to form modified binders [1].

The fatigue life of AC critically influences maintenance costs and is affected by the material's ability to resist cyclic heavy traffic loads across varying environmental conditions without significant cracking [2–4]. Degradation of AC primarily stems from the aging of the bituminous binder due to oxidation, limiting its resistance to repetitive tensile stresses [5, 6], with failure occurring when tensile strain exceeds the material's capacity [7]. Additionally, cold conditions increase material brittleness and susceptibility to thermally-induced cracking [8], whereas high temperatures render the binder more viscous and prone to deformation [9].

Several factors such as binder content [8], air voids content [10, 11], loading strain [12, 13], and operational temperature [13, 14] influence AC's fatigue resistance. Common laboratory assessments include four-point bending, semi-circular bending, and indirect tensile tests, each offering insights into fatigue life, stiffness, and strength under varied loading conditions [15–21].

Accurately predicting fatigue life relative to AC composition, climate, and loading rate is essential for effective mix design, though traditional testing is notably time-intensive, requiring up to 42 days for specimen preparation, with tests lasting several hours to days based on load and frequency [22]. Although these methods provide deep insights, they demand substantial time and resources. By applying machine learning (ML) models to existing datasets, predictions of AC's fatigue life become feasible when traditional testing is not viable.

Extensive reviews have been conducted on the mechanisms, characterization techniques, and mitigation strategies in AC fatigue life, pointing to the complex interplay between material components and external factors such as aging and environmental impacts [2, 3, 23, 24]. Recent developments in ML-assisted mix design have initiated models incorporating a wider array of variables to predict fatigue life [25–27]. Our research aims to utilize a comprehensive dataset to model ML relationships focusing primarily on easily measurable properties during the design phase, such as binder content (%) and air voids (%), along with the type of binder and penetration grade. These microstructural parameters were recently highlighted by Alnaqbi et al. [28] as crucial for the durability of AC pavements. To our knowledge, the detailed analysis and extensive application of neural networks in predicting laboratory specimen fatigue life have not been extensively reported in existing literature.

2 Methodology

The primary aim of this study was to compare the performance of various artificial neural network (ANN) models, each utilizing different combinations of input

parameters. This comparative approach allowed for the determination of which parameters are most critical for the construction of predictive models and which are less influential. Initially, a principal model were developed utilizing all available input parameters. Subsequent models were then created, each lacking one of these input parameters, to isolate and evaluate the impact of each parameter on the model's predictive accuracy.

2.1 Data Collection

Data for this study were collected from sample preparation and measurements carried out at two institutions: the Faculty of Civil Engineering at the Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU) and the Faculty of Civil Engineering at the Warsaw University of Technology (WUT). For the purposes of this study, selected data included: binder content (%), binder type—modified bituminous binders (PMB) and neat bituminous binders (NB), air voids (%), loading strain (ϵ), penetration grade ($\times 0.1$ mm), test temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), initial stiffness (MPa), and number of cycles (N_f).

The polymer-modified bitumens (PMBs) were enhanced using a styrene-butadiene-styrene elastomer, improving their resilience and performance characteristics [29]. Neat bitumens (NBs), also referred to as paving grade bitumens, were prepared in various grades such as 35/50, 50/70, and 70/100, each affecting the penetration values significantly [30]. All experiments were consistently performed at a temperature of 10°C and a loading frequency of 10 Hz using a four-point bending setup. The initial dataset comprised 152 samples, with 102 samples from CTU and 50 from the WUT laboratory (Table 1). A significant benefit of this study is the provision of these datasets alongside the codes on our GitHub repository¹, making them readily available for further research. These datasets are extremely valuable, offering a robust foundation for future explorations into asphalt concrete behavior under varied conditions.

Outlier detection was implemented using the Z-score technique, where:

$$Z = \frac{X - \mu}{\sigma}. \quad (1)$$

Here, Z is the Z-score, representing the number of standard deviations a data point X differs from the mean μ of the dataset, with σ being the standard deviation indicating the dispersion of data points around the mean. For optimal data filtration, samples with $Z \geq 3$ were excluded as outliers.

¹ https://github.com/jakub-houlik/Asphalt_Fatigue_ANN

Table 1 Summary of data gathered for modelling. Both datasets (CTU and WUT) consisted of PMB and NB. The values for the Combined dataset was filtered by applying the Z-score cut-off.

Laboratory	Binder content (%)	Penetration (0.1mm)	Air voids (%)	Strain ($\times 10^{-6}$)	Initial stiffness (MPa)	N_f ($\times 10^3$)	Samples
CTU	3.9–5.7	40–85	3.1–11.6	110–300	3,666–17,428	3.4–1,668	102
WUT	3.9–4.6	40–60	3.9–8.0	90–210	11,083–17,574	50.1–9,810	50
Combined	3.9–5.1	40–85	3.2–7.0	90–210	6,598–17,574	10.4–2,519	118

2.2 ANN

The primary goal of this study was to compare the performance of various ANN models, each utilizing different combinations of input parameters to ascertain which parameters are most significant for predicting fatigue life. Initially, a principal model was created with all available input parameters, accompanied by a systematic search for optimal hyperparameters to enhance model performance and accuracy.

To identify the best hyperparameters, we implemented cross-validation and split the data into three groups (folds). Each cycle of training and validation involved using one fold for validation and the others for training. This cycle was repeated, rotating the validation fold each time, which helped create multiple models with different training-validation data splits. We always allocated 20% of the dataset for testing, with the remaining 80% divided into the three folds for the cross-validation process. This approach minimized the risk of bias in model performance due to random data selection.

The input data for the model are provided along with the ANN’s structure in Fig. 1, indicating the optimized architecture parameters: number of hidden layers, n_h , and number of neurons in the hidden layer, $n_{\text{neur,h}}$. The input parameters follow the data prepared during the experimental session (Table 1). The distribution of numeric input parameters is provided in Fig. 2. N_f was the only output parameter.

After finding the optimum ANN size and hyperparameters, models were crafted with one input parameter omitted at a time, allowing for the evaluation of the importance of each parameter. Models were for 200,000 epochs, aiming to optimize the model to achieve the lowest validation loss. The model considered most accurate was saved at the point where it exhibited the lowest validation loss.

Such an ANN model was highly effective for processing tabular numerical data; the model assigned weights to different input variables and combined them through several hidden layers to generate the output. These weights were adjusted based on validation data through multiple iterations to improve the model’s accuracy.

2.2.1 Activation Functions

In neural networks, activation functions are crucial for introducing non-linear properties into the model, allowing it to learn more complex patterns. The activation

Fig. 1 ANN's architecture, input parameters, and the output parameter.

Fig. 2 Distributions of numeric parameters for ANNs.

functions used in this study included ReLU, SiLU, GELU, and Mish, each with specific properties suitable for different network configurations:

1. ReLU (rectified linear unit) function, defined as $f(x) = \max(0, x)$, facilitates faster training by effectively turning off the negative part of its input [31].
2. SiLU (sigmoid linear unit) function, defined as $f(x) = \frac{x}{1+e^{-x}}$, introduces a non-monotonic function that helps the network learn more complex patterns [32].
3. GELU (Gaussian error linear unit) function, using the formula $f(x) = x \Phi(x)$ where $\Phi(x)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard Gaussian, offers a probabilistic approach to gating inputs [33].
4. Mish function is defined as $f(x) = x \tanh(\ln(1 + e^x))$, providing a smooth and non-monotonic activation that has shown success in deeper or more complex architectures [34].

2.2.2 Optimizers

An optimizer is a crucial algorithm used to minimize a loss function, which is a measure of how well a model's predictions match the actual outcomes. The optimizer adjusts the weights of the network with the aim of reducing the loss, thereby improving the model's accuracy during training. The choice of optimizer is critical for training neural networks efficiently and effectively, as it directly influences the speed and quality of learning [35]. In this study, the following optimizers were evaluated:

1. Adam: An optimizer that computes adaptive learning rates for each parameter from estimates of first and second moments of the gradients.
2. AdamW: A variant of Adam with decoupled weight decay regularization, helping to improve training stability.
3. RMSprop: Utilizes the moving average of squared gradients to normalize the gradient itself, a good choice for recurrent neural networks.
4. Stochastic gradient descent (SGD): Utilizes mini-batched gradient descent with a defined learning rate and momentum, known for its simplicity and effectiveness in various scenarios.

2.2.3 Loss Functions

Selecting the appropriate loss function is crucial when training neural networks because it defines the measure of error between the predicted values and the actual values that the model aims to minimize. This error quantification directly influences how the model learns during training, guiding the adjustment of weights to optimize performance. A well-chosen loss function ensures that the model accurately captures the underlying patterns of the dataset, particularly in tasks where the scale of data varies significantly. In this study, two types of loss functions were utilized to tailor the model's performance to the diverse scales of fatigue life data, typically represented on a logarithmic scale:

1. Commonly used mean square error (MSE): This loss function calculates the average squared difference between the predicted and actual values, suitable for regression problems. It is defined as:

$$L_{\text{MSE}}(N_f, \hat{N}_f) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (N_{f,i} - \hat{N}_{f,i})^2, \quad (2)$$

where $N_{f,i}$ is the measured number of cycles, $\hat{N}_{f,i}$ is the predicted number of cycles, and n is the number of samples.

2. Mean square logarithmic error (MSLE): This loss function is particularly useful when the target variable, like fatigue life, spans several orders of magnitude. It computes the mean of the squared logarithmic differences between the predicted and actual values, helping to prevent large errors in the predictions of large true values. It is defined as:

$$L_{\text{MSLE}}(N_f, \hat{N}_f) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\log(N_{f,i} + 1) - \log(\hat{N}_{f,i} + 1))^2. \quad (3)$$

The ANN model configuration and training were executed as follows: The Sequential model from the Keras library (version 2.12.0rc1) was utilized, and before training, the data were normalized using the *MinMaxScaler* function from the *sklearn.preprocessing* module to scale the input variables between 0 and 1. The configured hyperparameters included the number of hidden layers (n_h), number of neurons within the hidden layers ($n_{\text{neur,h}}$), activation function, and the optimization algorithm, as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2 Hyperparameters tested during the model development and values selected for the final model.

Hyperparameter	Grid	Selected
Loss function	$L_{\text{MSE}}, L_{\text{MSLE}}$	both
Optimizer	Adam, AdamW, RMSprop, SGD	SGD (for L_{MSE}) and RMSprop (for L_{MSLE})
Activation function	ReLU, SiLU, GELU, Mish	SiLU (for L_{MSE}) and ReLU (for L_{MSLE})
n_h	1, 2, 3	2
$n_{\text{neur,h}}$	10, 20, 50, 100, 200	10 (for L_{MSE}) and 20 (for L_{MSLE})

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Hyperparameters

The use of SiLU and ReLU activation functions was instrumental in mitigating the vanishing gradient problem, facilitating effective error backpropagation through the

network [36]. Our detailed examination aimed to determine the optimal settings for the number of hidden layers (n_h) and the number of neurons per hidden layer ($n_{neur,h}$), tested against both L_{MSE} and L_{MSLE} loss functions.

For the model employing L_{MSE} , the configuration with $n_h = 2$ and $n_{neur,h} = 10$ proved most effective, as depicted in Fig. 3. This structure achieved the highest average $\overline{R^2}$ score across the three folds, where some combinations of hyperparameters resulted in $\overline{R^2}$ scores below zero, indicating a predictive ability worse than the mean of the dataset.

Fig. 3 Variation of the model performance, measured by the $\overline{R^2}$ score, in relation to n_h and $n_{neur,h}$ when employing L_{MSE} as the loss function.

Conversely, the logarithmic model using L_{MSLE} with the same number of hidden layers and 20 neurons per layer showed optimal performance, as demonstrated in Fig. 4. Certain configurations failed to converge and were excluded from the results, while some resulted in negative $\overline{R^2}$ scores, similarly indicating less predictive power than the average dataset value.

When assessing different optimizers, the SGD optimizer paired with the SiLU activation function showcased superior performance, particularly with L_{MSE} . In contrast, the RMSprop optimizer was more effective with the ReLU activation function for L_{MSLE} , as depicted in Fig. 5. RMSprop’s method of adjusting the learning rate using a moving average of squared gradients provides stability in noisy data environments [35].

Fig. 4 Variation of the model performance, measured by the $\overline{R^2}$ score, in relation to n_h and $n_{neur,h}$ when employing L_{MSLE} as the loss function.

Fig. 5 Model performance in relation to activation functions and optimizers used, showcasing different predictive abilities and optimal hyperparameter combinations for both loss functions.

3.2 Model accuracy

Table 3 presents the R^2 scores for models trained on the entire dataset post Z -score filtering as listed in Table 1. These models were optimized for architecture and hyperparameters, using all inputs depicted in Fig. 1 as well as scenarios where individual parameters were omitted. Despite substantial efforts to optimize the architecture and

ANN’s parameters, the general results were relatively poor. This outcome likely stems from the large variance in the input data, a characteristic common in AC fatigue life measurements, and the challenging nature of acquiring vast, high-quality datasets [37, 38].

Table 3 R^2 scores for fully optimized models under different loss functions and for models with missing input parameters.

	L_{MSE}	L_{MSLE}
All inputs	0.376	0.301
Without initial stiffness	0.296	0.099
Without type of binder	0.114	-0.026
Without penetration of binder	0.320	0.145
Without air voids	0.374	0.141
Without loading strain	0.374	0.087
Without binder content	0.396	-0.153

Interestingly, the models performed differently under linear and logarithmic conditions. For the linear model, excluding the binder content unexpectedly resulted in slightly better performance, a counterintuitive result suggesting potential issues with data sensitivity or model overfitting. Parameters like binder content, initial strain, and air voids showed minimal impact on model performance, which could indicate redundancy or correlations within the inputs. Conversely, for the logarithmic model, the inclusion of all parameters led to the highest accuracy, confirming the importance of a comprehensive dataset.

Training dynamics also varied significantly between models using different loss functions. The L_{MSE} model quickly reached a minimum validation loss, but then diverged, indicating potential overfitting or an inability to generalize from the training data (Fig. 6). The L_{MSLE} model exhibited a more complex pattern, experiencing local minima before stabilizing at a global minimum after about 120,000 epochs, suggesting that it may be better suited for handling the logarithmic distribution of fatigue life data.

Comparisons of model predictions with actual data underscored these observations. While both L_{MSE} and L_{MSLE} models achieved similar overall R^2 scores, the linear model struggled particularly with lower N_f values, as seen in the scatter from the line of equality in true versus predicted plots (Figures 7 and 8). This variance highlights the advantages of using L_{MSLE} for distributions characterized by a wide range of values. When comparing the plots in Figs. 7 and 8, it is clear that the ANN model cannot predict N_f accurately unless providing the information about the binder type as the binder modifications have major impact on the fatigue life [39].

Fig. 6 Training convergence plots illustrating the model's learning process over 200,000 epochs for both L_{MSE} and L_{MSLE} .

Fig. 7 Comparison of true versus predicted values for the entire dataset, using both loss functions.

Fig. 8 Impact of omitting the binder type parameter on model predictions, using both loss functions; the plots when compared with Fig. 7 clearly show the importance of the binder type parameter.

3.3 Practical outcomes

Further analysis involved generating partial dependence plots to explore the relationships between input parameters and predicted N_f values for both linear and logarithmic models. These plots, illustrated in Figures 9 and 10, were carefully constructed to adhere to the scatter distribution of the input data, avoiding extrapolation that could lead to unreliable results. Input data points are marked with white triangular markers on these plots. Predictions were executed for scenarios where the binder type was either PMB or NB, highlighting the significant effect binder type has on the predicted fatigue life, with PMB showing considerably higher predicted N_f values.

The plots also demonstrate dependencies on binder content and initial stiffness, with other parameters set to median values: strain at 150 microstrain, penetration of binder at 60×0.1 mm, and air voids at 5.3%. The explored ranges for binder content were from 3.9% to 5.1%, and for initial stiffness from 6.598 GPa to 17.574 GPa.

Analysis of model performance indicates that as stiffness increases, so does the predicted number of fatigue cycles (N_f). A slight increase in N_f with higher binder content was also observed. From these findings, it is advisable to use PMB, which significantly impacts N_f , and to prefer higher binder contents, around 5%. Initial stiffness serves as a useful indicator of N_f , particularly when using NB.

Supporting these observations, a study by Sarsam [40] suggested that asphalt fatigue life increases with higher bituminous binder content, particularly noticeable at lower strain levels, confirming the influence of binder content on increasing fatigue

Fig. 9 Partial dependence plots for the linear model trained with L_{MSE} , showing how different input parameters relate to predicted N_f across two binder types.

Fig. 10 Partial dependence plots for the logarithmic model trained with L_{MSLE} , displaying the influence of input parameters on predicted N_f for different binder types.

capacity. Additionally, study by Lundstrom et al. [24] discussed the relationship between binder penetration, initial stiffness, and fatigue life, noting that higher initial stiffness correlates with an increased number of fatigue cycles, suggesting that a stiffer binder, which generally has lower penetration, tends to withstand more fatigue cycles.

These results align with findings by Zeiada et al. [41], who reported a significant increase in N_f with higher binder content, and Ma et al. [38], who highlighted the impact of non-uniform distribution of air voids on fatigue life. Moreover, a study by Yan et al. [37] on constructing an ANN for N_f prediction also supports the notion that while air voids do not significantly affect fatigue life, increased binder content does enhance N_f values.

4 Conclusion

This study has effectively leveraged artificial neural networks (ANNs) to predict the fatigue life of asphalt concrete (AC), illustrating the substantial influence of binder type and content on durability. Through meticulous optimization of hyperparameters and architecture in our models, we have adapted to the complexities inherent in the varied data of AC fatigue life. Our tailored models utilized a significant dataset, consisting of 152 samples collected and tested in our own laboratories, underscoring the authenticity and relevance of our research findings.

Our results demonstrate that modified bituminous binders (PMB) significantly enhance fatigue life predictions compared to neat bituminous binders (NB). Despite extensive hyperparameter tuning—including adjustments in the number of hidden layers and neurons—the models achieved moderate overall accuracies, with the best R^2 scores below 0.4. This moderate performance highlights the challenges posed by the substantial variability and scattered nature of AC fatigue life data.

The importance of each input parameter was clearly underscored, revealing that the omission of critical inputs such as binder type or initial stiffness significantly alters the predictions. This study not only confirms the critical roles of comprehensive input parameters for accurate modeling but also emphasizes the effectiveness of hyperparameter tuning in capturing the true variability of fatigue life data.

In addition to the machine-learning outcomes, the practical implications of our findings are significant. The analysis points to the potential of using higher binder content and modified binders to enhance fatigue life, providing actionable insights for pavement engineering practices.

Looking ahead, the expansion of dataset size and diversity is crucial for improving model robustness and general applicability in pavement engineering. Future research should explore hybrid models that integrate empirical methods with machine learning to further enhance prediction accuracy and reliability. All codes for training,

validation, and the final models have been made available to the research community in our open repository, facilitating transparency and encouraging further research.

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this chapter.

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References

- [1] J. Valentin, J. Trejbal, V. Nežerka, T. Valentová, P. Vacková, P. Tichá, A comprehensive study on adhesion between modified bituminous binders and mineral aggregates, *Construction and Building Materials* 305 (2021) 124686. doi : 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.124686.
- [2] M. M. Isied, M. I. Souliman, Integrated predictive artificial neural network fatigue endurance limit model for asphalt concrete pavements, *Canadian Journal of Civil Engineering* 46 (2019) 114–123. doi : 10.1139/cjce-2018-0051.
- [3] F. Xiao, S. Amirkhanian, C. H. Juang, Prediction of fatigue life of rubberized asphalt concrete mixtures containing reclaimed asphalt pavement using artificial neural networks, *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering* 21 (2009) 253–261. doi : 10.1061/(asce)0899-1561(2009)21:6(253).
- [4] B. Shi, Q. Dong, X. Chen, X. Gu, X. Wang, S. Yan, A comprehensive review on the fatigue resistance of recycled asphalt materials: Influential factors, correlations and improvements, *Construction and Building Materials* 384 (2023) 131435. doi : 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.131435.
- [5] C. A. Bell, D. Sosnovske, J. Wieder, Aging: binder validation, Strategic Highway Research Program, National Research Council Washington, DC, 1994.
- [6] S. Sreedhar, E. Coleri, The effect of long-term aging on fatigue cracking resistance of asphalt mixtures, *International Journal of Pavement Engineering* 23 (2020) 308–320. doi : 10.1080/10298436.2020.1745206.
- [7] N. D. Beskou, S. V. Tsinopoulos, G. D. Hatzigeorgiou, Fatigue cracking failure criterion for flexible pavements under moving vehicles, *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* 90 (2016) 476–479. doi : 10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.09.019.
- [8] E. Maczka, P. Mackiewicz, Asphalt mixtures fatigue life considering various environmental impacts, *Materials* 16(2023)966. doi : 10.3390/ma16030966.
- [9] F. Moreno-Navarro, M. Sol-Sánchez, G. García-Travé, M. C. Rubio-Gámez, Fatigue cracking in asphalt mixtures: the effects of ageing and temperature, *Road Materials and Pavement Design* 19 (2017) 561–570. doi : 10.1080/14680629.2018.1418717.
- [10] A. J. Enríquez-León, T. D. de Souza, F. T. S. Aragão, D. Braz, A. M. B. Pereira, L. P. Nogueira, Determination of the air void content of asphalt concrete mixtures using artificial intelligence techniques to segment micro-CT images, *International Journal of Pavement Engineering* 23 (2021) 3973–3982. doi : 10.1080/10298436.2021.1931197.
- [11] F. Praticò, A. Moro, Measurement of air void content in hot mix asphalts: Method and core diameter dependence, *Construction and Building Materials* 26 (2012) 344–349. doi : 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2011.06.032.
- [12] M.-C. Liao, J.-S. Chen, K.-W. Tsou, Fatigue characteristics of bitumen-filler mastics and asphalt mixtures, *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering* 24 (2012) 916–923. doi : 10.1061/(asce)mt.1943-5533.0000450.
- [13] Y. Zhang, J. Zhang, T. Ma, H. Qi, C. Chen, Predicting asphalt mixture fatigue life via four-point bending tests based on viscoelastic continuum dam-

- age mechanics, *Case Studies in Construction Materials* 19 (2023) e02671. doi:10.1016/j.cscm.2023.e02671.
- [14] K. Yang, H. Cui, X. Ma, M. Zhu, Understanding and characterizing the fatigue cracking resistance of asphalt binder at intermediate temperature: A literature review, *Construction and Building Materials* 407 (2023) 133432. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.133432.
- [15] H. Cheng, J. Liu, L. Sun, L. Liu, Y. Zhang, Fatigue behaviours of asphalt mixture at different temperatures in four-point bending and indirect tensile fatigue tests, *Construction and Building Materials* 273 (2021) 121675. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.121675.
- [16] H. Cheng, L. Sun, Y. Wang, L. Liu, X. Chen, Fatigue test setups and analysis methods for asphalt mixture: A state-of-the-art review, *Journal of Road Engineering* 2 (2022) 279–308. doi:10.1016/j.jreng.2022.11.002.
- [17] N. Sudarsanan, Y. R. Kim, A critical review of the fatigue life prediction of asphalt mixtures and pavements, *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering (English Edition)* 9 (2022) 808–835. doi:10.1016/j.jtte.2022.05.003.
- [18] G. Saha, K. P. Biligiri, Fracture damage evaluation of asphalt mixtures using semi-circular bending test based on fracture energy approach, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 142 (2015) 154–169. doi:10.1016/j.engfracmech.2015.06.009.
- [19] P. Zielinski, The use of the semi-circular bending method to assess the intermediate-temperature fracture toughness of asphalt concrete mixes with reclaimed asphalt shingles, *Road Materials and Pavement Design* 25 (2023) 81–98. doi:10.1080/14680629.2023.2194432.
- [20] M. T. Nguyen, H. J. Lee, J. Baek, Fatigue analysis of asphalt concrete under indirect tensile mode of loading using crack images, *Journal of Testing and Evaluation* 41 (2012) 104589. doi:10.1520/jte104589.
- [21] T. Vishnu, Laboratory investigation on the fatigue performance of asphalt mixes reinforced with human hair fiber in pavement application, *Materials Today: Proceedings* doi:10.1016/j.matpr.2023.01.070.
- [22] CEN, EN 12697-24: 2018; Bituminous Mixtures—Test Methods—Part 24: Resistance to Fatigue, European Standard.
- [23] Z. Wang, D. Liu, B. Hu, C. Zhu, W. Luo, An improved regression model to predict fatigue life of asphalt mixes incorporating low to moderate RAP contents, *Construction and Building Materials* 374 (2023) 130904. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.130904.
- [24] R. Lundstrom, H. D. Benedetto, U. Isacsson, Influence of asphalt mixture stiffness on fatigue failure, *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering* 16 (2004) 516–525. doi:10.1061/(asce)0899-1561(2004)16:6(516).
- [25] J. Chen, Y. Liu, Fatigue modeling using neural networks: A comprehensive review, *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures* 45 (2022) 945–979. doi:10.1111/ffe.13640.

- [26] R. Hooda, V. Joshi, M. Shah, A comprehensive review of approaches to detect fatigue using machine learning techniques, *Chronic Diseases and Translational Medicine* 8 (2022) 26–35. doi:10.1016/j.cdtm.2021.07.002.
- [27] Z. Lian, M. Li, W. Lu, Fatigue life prediction of aluminum alloy via knowledge-based machine learning, *International Journal of Fatigue* 157 (2022) 106716. doi:10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2021.106716.
- [28] A. J. Alnaqbi, W. Zeiada, G. Al-Khateeb, A. Abttan, M. Abuzwidah, Predictive models for flexible pavement fatigue cracking based on machine learning, *Transportation Engineering* 16 (2024) 100243. doi:10.1016/j.treng.2024.100243.
- [29] S. Dziadosz, M. S lowik, F. Niwczyk, M. Bilski, Study on styrene-butadiene-styrene modified asphalt binders relaxation at low temperature, *Materials* 14 (2021) 2888. doi:10.3390/ma14112888.
- [30] A. R. Pasandín, I. Pérez, Effects of the asphalt penetration grade and the mineralogical composition on the asphalt-aggregate bond, *Petroleum Science and Technology* 32 (2014) 2730–2737. doi:10.1080/10916466.2013.879175.
- [31] K. Hara, D. Saito, H. Shouno, Analysis of function of rectified linear unit used in deep learning, in: 2015 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), 2015. doi:10.1109/ijcnn.2015.7280578.
- [32] S. Elfwing, E. Uchibe, K. Doya, Sigmoid-weighted linear units for neural network function approximation in reinforcement learning, *Neural Networks* 107 (2018) 3–11. doi:10.1016/j.neunet.2017.12.012.
- [33] D. Hendrycks, K. Gimpel, Gaussian error linear units (GELUs), arXiv: Learning. URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:125617073>
- [34] M. A. Mercioni, S. Holban, Soft clipping Mish - a novel activation function for deep learning, in: 2021 4th International Conference on Information and Computer Technologies (ICICT), 2021. doi:10.1109/iciict52872.2021.00010.
- [35] Y.-L. Peng, W.-P. Lee, Practical guidelines for resolving the loss divergence caused by the root-mean-squared propagation optimizer, *Applied Soft Computing* 153 (2024) 111335. doi:10.1016/j.asoc.2024.111335.
- [36] A. Jentzen, A. Riekert, Convergence analysis for gradient flows in the training of artificial neural networks with ReLU activation, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* 517 (2023) 126601. doi:10.1016/j.jmaa.2022.126601.
- [37] C. Yan, R. Gao, W. Huang, Asphalt mixture fatigue life prediction model based on neural network, in: CICTP 2017, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2018. doi:10.1061/9780784480915.136.
- [38] T. Ma, Y. Zhang, D. Zhang, J. Yan, Q. Ye, Influences by air voids on fatigue life of asphalt mixture based on discrete element method, *Construction and Building Materials* 126 (2016) 785–799. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.09.045.

- [39] M. Seif, M. Abbasi, Evaluation of fatigue behavior of modified asphalt binders using of dissipated energy approach, *Exploratory Materials Science Research* 3 (2022) 116. doi : 10.47204/emsr.3.2.2022.116-123.
- [40] S. I. Sarsam, Sensitivity of the fatigue life of asphalt concrete to testing variables, *Journal of Transportation Engineering and Traffic Management* 3 (2022) 1-10.
- [41] W. A. Zeiada, K. E. Kaloush, B. S. Underwood, M. S. Mamlouk, Effect of Air Voids and Asphalt Content on Fatigue Damage Using the Viscoelastic Continuum Damage Analysis, *American Society of Civil Engineers*, 2013. doi : 10.1061/9780784413005.094.